

Assessment of Material Resource Management Practices On Administration of Public Universities in South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated assessment of material resource management practices on administration of public universities in South-South, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The design adopted for the study was descriptive survey design. The population was 11,174 staff from four public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria. A sample size of 559 staff was used were selected for the study. The sample was selected using a multi-stage sampling procedure technique. The instrument for data collection was researchers-structured questionnaire titled “Material Resource Management Practices and Administration Questionnaire (MRMPAQ)”. The questionnaire was validated by three experts in Faculty of Education Benue State University, Makurdi. A reliability test of the instrument was conducted on 30 staff from University of Calabar, Nigeria, using Cronbach Alpha. The result yielded a value index of 0.92 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. Chi-square test of goodness of fit was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that material resource planning and purchasing practices have positive significant impact on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria. The study concluded that material resource management practices have improved administration of public universities. The study recommended that public university administrators in Nigeria should ensure regular and proper material resources management focused on planning and purchasing of material resources in their universities in order to enhance administration of public universities in Nigeria.

Keywords: Material resource management, planning, purchasing, administration of public universities

Introduction

Administration is an essential activity in any formal organization including public universities. It is for this reason that one may rightly say that for any organization to achieve success, effective administration cannot be overemphasized. Globally, there have been issues of ineffective administration of public universities over the years. Universities seem to be confronted with numerous challenges. Romina (2023) opines that some of the issues confronting higher education across the globe including Nigerian universities are lack of fund, lack of facilities, frequent labour disputes and closure of universities, inadequate resources and ineffective material resources management. Although Nigerian government and higher education administrators seem to address these issues, Nigerian universities still seem to experience ineffective administration. Administration is the prudent management of scarce and available resources with emphasis on high degree of accountability from subordinates directed towards the achievement of goals and objectives (Venkatesh, 2021). It involves the evaluation and appraisal of results of educational efforts for the purpose of entrenching accountability to all those who have interest in educational enterprise like public universities.

Public universities are higher institutions of learning owned and managed by federal and state governments. Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) describes these institutions as citadels of learning for promoting academic excellence for national growth. Public universities are essential for training and development of top level manpower. Bachelor’s degrees and higher degrees such as masters and doctor of philosophy (PhD) degrees are awarded by universities. The importance of public universities cannot be emphasized due to its centrality in the nation’s development. The government of Nigeria particularly Cross River and Akwa Ibom States seem to pay much attention to effective administration of public universities through provision of resources (human, material, financial, information and time). Despite this effort the public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States seem to experience deficient administration. Although, generally, Bua (2020) opines that problems

such as lack of administrative will, poor leadership, uncooperative attitudes of staff and lack of infrastructural facilities may account for ineffective administration of public universities in Nigeria.

In Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria, the problem of ineffective administration of public universities may be attributed to material resource management practices. Venkatesh (2021) describes material resource management practices as a coordinated effort to effectively manage the available material resources in the school to promote learning through careful planning, organizing, controlling, coordinating, utilization, maintenance and evaluation of available material resources in the school. The objective of material resource management is to attract material costs on all forms and to optimize the overall end results. Effective material resource management could promote administration of an organization. Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria administration of public universities seems not to be yielding the needed result. This may be due to administrators' inability to put in place effective material resources management practices such as planning and purchasing practices.

Planning is the first and foremost function of material resource management and administration of any school. Okwori (2023) defines planning as the determination of educational needs to ensure that limited educational resources are rationally allocated among the various competing educational demands and programmes. Therefore, material resource management in universities need effective planning so as to enhance effective administration of universities. This is because research by Nwafor (2017) found that secondary school teachers material resource skills in planning, coordination, controlling and organizing has significant impact on material resource management in secondary schools. Apali (2014) also found that effective material resource planning help to control inventory levels and schedule replenishment; material resource planning promotes effective inventory management and guides the coordination of materials at different stages of production process. However, Ogbuanya, et al. (2017) in their study revealed that there was no significant difference in mean responses of the respondents on the planning, organizing, controlling and coordinating strategies for proper management of material resources for effective teaching of electrical/electronic technology education. It is through planning that university administrators may identify resource needs of the universities and may decide on the right quality and quantity for purchasing.

Purchasing material resources is a necessary practice for effective school administration especially in universities where it seems there is high demand for utilization of material resources. Purchasing of material resources for administration of universities may mean the process of determining and deciding on procurement of the needed resources and its supply in universities. Izuagie (2015) maintains that the major function of purchasing embraces the flow of materials from the supplies to an organization which has the intention of facilitating the attainment of predetermined objectives. Apali (2014) revealed a positive and significant relationship between material resource management and effective purchasing. Demise (2018) found that schools do not apply purchasing process as planned, there is low maintenance activities in the schools and lack of appropriate training for administrative services. Purchasing simply describes the process of buying; however in a broader sense, it involves determining the need, selecting the supplier, arriving at a proper price terms and condition, issuing the contract or order and following up to ensure proper delivery.

Although, government, university administrators and relevant stakeholders of universities such as donor agencies, World Bank, philanthropists and unions seem to support effective administration of public universities through provision of material resources, this effort seems to be an exercise in futility. Observation by the researchers, government and university administrators in Nigeria particularly in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria, that administration of public universities is still plagued with the issue of material resource management practices. There seem to be shortage of material resources such as classroom facilities, office equipment, laboratories equipment and library facilities. It is a worrisome and a matter of continuous concern that some of the material resources were not forecasted or determined in number and quantity to be used in universities while others such as instructional materials and utilities seem to be in short supply probably due to lack of proper purchasing practice. All these seem to hinder effective administration of public universities. It is based on the above background that the study sought to carry out assessment of material resource management practices on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study was to investigate assessment of material resource management practices on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the impact of material resource planning practice on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria
2. Ascertain the impact of material resource purchasing practice on administration of public universities South-South, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the impact of material resource planning practice on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria?
2. What is the impact of material resource purchasing practice on administration of public universities South-South, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Material resources planning practice has no significant impact on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria
2. Material resources purchasing practice has no significant impact on administration of public universities South-South, Nigeria

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design for carrying out the study. The population for the study comprises 11,174 academic and non-academic staff from four public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria (Planning, Research and Statistics Department of Federal Ministry of Education (2021). The sample size for the study comprises 559 or 5% of the 11,174 academic and non academic staff in 4 public universities in the study area. The sample was selected using multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled “Material Resource Management Practices and Administration Questionnaire (MRMPAQ)”. It contained 10 items on the two variables of the study which are material resource planning and material resource purchasing. The questionnaire was structured on a four point rating scale with response modes of Strongly Agree (SA)=4, Agree (A)=3, Disagree (D)=2 and Strongly Disagree (SD)=1. For content and construct validity, the questionnaire was validated by three experts in Faculty of Education Benue State University, Makurdi. For internal consistency, a reliability test of the instrument was conducted on 30 staff from University of Cross River State Calabar using Cronbach Alpha and the result yielded 0.92. The data obtained from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean scores and standard deviations to answer the research questions. Decision was based on the mean cut off point of 2.50. Any mean score below 2.50 was not regarded as agree, while mean scores of 2.50 and above was regarded as agree. Chi-square test of goodness of fit was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule of the chi-square is that if the chi-square calculated is greater than p-value of 0.000 the null hypothesis is not rejected but if it is less than 0.000, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the impact of material resources planning practice on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Rating on Impact of Material Resources Planning Practice on Administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria

S/No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Specific objectives for using material resource are formulated to achieve university goals.	559	156	277	96	30	2.98	0.80	Agree
2	Material resources are planned based on university needs to enhance university administration.	559	158	90	162	149	2.59	1.14	Agree
3	Standards are set using office equipment to enhance school administration.	559	205	154	140	60	2.86	1.01	Agree
4	Teaching materials are planned in advance for achieving universities goals in producing quality students.	559	137	230	122	70	2.73	0.94	Agree
5	Lack of proper planning for material resources will inhibit achievement of university objectives	559	189	156	106	108	2.72	1.11	Agree
Cluster Mean							2.77		Agree

Source: Researcher’s Field Work, 2025

Table 1 shows Mean ratings of 2.96, 2.59, 2.86, 2.73, 2.72, and cluster mean 2.77 with a corresponding Standard Deviation ratings of 0.80, 1.14, 1.01, 0.94 and 1.11 respectively. The result indicated that items 1-5 individual ratings agreed that specific objectives for using material resource are formulated to achieve university goals, material resources are planned based on university needs to enhance university administration, standards are set using office equipment to enhance school administration, teaching materials are planned in advance for achieving universities goals in producing quality students and lack of proper planning for material resources will inhibit achievement of university objectives. The cluster Mean value of 2.77 was found to be above the Mean score benchmark of 2.50. This shows positive impact of impact of material resources planning practice on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.

Research Question 2:

What is the impact of material resources purchasing practice on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Rating on impact of Material Resources Purchasing Practice on Administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria

S/No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	Cost of purchasing material resources needed in universities is determined by the administrators.	559	177	251	13	118	2.83	1.07	Agree
7	Timely purchase of material resources enhances effective universities administration.	559	234	215	68	85	2.88	1.03	Agree
8	Proper negotiation of the cost of material resources is carried out before they are purchased.	559	182	163	68	113	2.82	1.13	Agree
9	High cost of material resources lead to less purchase thus, inhibiting university administration.	559	242	223	103	69	2.82	0.97	Agree
10	Material resources are supplied in universities in the right quantity no matter the cost.	559	215	196	122	72	2.77	0.99	Agree
Cluster Mean							2.82		Agree

Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2025

Table 2 shows Mean ratings of 2.83, 2.88, 2.82, 2.82, 2.77, and cluster mean 2.82 with a corresponding Standard Deviation ratings of 1.07, 1.03, 1.13, 0.97 and 0.99 respectively. The result indicated that items 6-10 individual ratings agreed that cost of purchasing material resources needed in universities is determined by the administrators, timely purchase of material resources enhances effective universities administration, proper negotiation of the cost of material resources is carried out before they are purchased, high cost of material resources lead to less purchase thus, inhibiting university administration and material resources are supplied in universities in the right quantity no matter the cost. The cluster Mean value of 2.82 was found to be above the Mean score benchmark of 2.50. This shows positive impact of material resources purchasing practice on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Material resources planning practice has no significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.

Table 8: Chi-square Analysis Summary of Impact of Material Resources Planning Practice on Administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.

Responses	Frequency Observed	Frequency Expected	P-Value	Df	χ^2 Cal.	Decision
SA	169	139/75	0.000	3	242.326 ^a	Sig.
A	181	139.75				
D	126	139.75				

SD	83	139.75
Total	559	

Source: Researcher’s Field Work 2025

Table 3 showed Chi-square calculated value of 242.326^a at 3 degree of freedom; P=0.000 is less than 0.05. With this result, the null hypothesis which states that, material resources planning practice has no significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria was rejected. This can be interpreted to mean that material resources planning practice has positive significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2:

Material resources purchasing practice has no significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.

Table 4: *Chi-square Analysis Summary of Impact of Material Resources Purchasing Practice on Administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.*

Responses	Frequency Observed	Frequency Expected	P-Value	df	x ² Cal.	Decision
SA	163	139.75				
A	139	139.75	0.000	3	215.985 ^a	Sig.
D	76	139.75				
SD	91	139.75				
Total	559					

Source: Researcher’s Field Work 2024

Table 4 showed Chi-square calculated value of 215.985^a degree of freedom; P=0.000 is less than 0.05. With this result, the null hypothesis which states that, material resources purchasing practice has no significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States was rejected. This can be interpreted to mean that material resources purchasing practice has positive significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of the study showed that material resources planning practice has positive significant impact on administration of Public Universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria. This finding means that specific objectives for using material resource are formulated to achieve university goals, material resources are planned based on university needs to enhance university administration, standards are set for using office equipment to enhance school administration, teaching materials are planned in advance for achieving universities goals in producing quality students and lack of proper planning for material resources will inhibit achievement of university objectives. This finding is in line with the findings of Nwafor (2017) whose finding shows that secondary school teachers material resource skills in planning, coordination, controlling and organizing has significant impact on material resource management in secondary schools. The finding is also in line with the findings of Apali (2014) whose finding shows that effective material resource planning help to control inventory levels and schedule replenishment; material resource planning promotes effective inventory management and guides the coordination of materials at different stages of production process. The finding of the study however disagree with the findings of Ogbuanya, Nweke and Ugwoke (2017) whose findings revealed that there was no significant difference in mean responses of the respondents on the planning, organizing, controlling and coordinating strategies for proper management of material resources for effective teaching of electrical/electronic technology education.

The second finding of the study showed that material resources purchasing practice has positive significant impact on administration of Public Universities. This finding means that the cost of purchasing material resources needed in universities is determined by the administrators, timely purchase of material resources enhances effective universities administration, proper negotiation of the cost of material resources is carried out before they are purchased, high cost of material resources lead to less purchase thus, inhibiting university administration and material resources are supplied in universities in the right quantity no matter the cost. This finding agreed with the finding of Apali (2014) whose findings revealed a positive and significant relationship between material resource management and effective purchasing. This finding however disagreed with the finding

of Demise (2018) whose finding showed that school do not apply purchasing process as planned, there is low maintenance activities in the schools and lack of appropriate training for administrative services.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that material resource management practices have enhanced administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria This implies that improvement in material resources planning, purchasing, organizing, controlling, coordinating, maintenance and evaluation practices have brought about significant positive improvement on administration of public universities in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States South-South, Nigeria

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made.

1. Public university administrators in Nigeria should ensure that there is proper planning of material resource management in their universities in order to enhance administration of public universities in the states.
2. The public university administrators should ensure that there is proper and adequate material resource purchasing practices that recognize taking stock of materials and with accurate costs to ensure the right purchase of materials resources for effective administration of public universities in Nigeria.

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